

THE DIFFICULTIES OF READING AMONG YOUNG LEARNERS IN ONLINE EDUCATION

Surmanov Sardor, EFL lecturer, TSUL
Email: s.surmanov@tsul.uz

Ametova Oyshajon, EFL lecturer, TSUL
Email: o.ametova@tsul.uz

&

Togaymurodova Rushana, EFL teacher,
Yeoju technical institute in Tashkent
Email: 12.1-03_TRF_1@ytit.uz

ABSTRACT

One of the most important skills that every pupil learn from the beginning of school is the ability to read to make meaning from text and learn through reading with online materials. The following article is devoted to the many concerns when an instructor faces pupils with reading difficulty. So what happens to a student when they have a learning difficulty or disability in reading and comprehension? What options are available to ensure that they do not slip through the cracks of the education system and are left behind?

Keywords: Young learners, poor reader, phonics, fluency, edcheckup, decoding.

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a complex cognitive process of decoding symbols aimed at understanding the text. One of the means of language acquisition, communication, exchange of information, ideas. According to S.F. Shatilov reading "refers to receptive types of speech activity and is a process of extracting information from a written text" [12]. The main practical goal of learning a foreign language in children is to improve their communicative competence, and through online education. The main tasks that must be completed when teaching younger students to read in English at the initial stage are: read aloud the text, understand the general content of the text and the main thing in it after a single reading. Read to yourself, fully understanding uncomplicated texts containing individual unfamiliar words. Read to yourself and understand the main content of the text, which includes a significant number of unfamiliar words.

A reading difficulty is a deficit in processes relating to decoding phonetic knowledge, word recognition and comprehension. These four simple factors can impact on overall reading skills. For instance, teaching every student in the first grade exactly how to decode words, how to understand phonetics, how to recognize words, and how to comprehend can represent various reading comprehension levels among learners.

The problem of teaching reading in a foreign language is one of the most important in the organization of the educational process in primary school.

Reading is one of the receptive types of speech activity, aimed at the perception and understanding of the written text, but it is included in the sphere of human communication and provides one of the forms of (written) communication in it [10]. Reading is one of the main means of obtaining information. The most important among the goals of teaching languages is

the formation of the ability to extract information from a graphically recorded text in the process of reading, which allows you to actively use the language being studied in various activities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The problem is that for a long time everybody believed that reading is a naturally acquired skill and that, we do not need to explicitly teach how to read. However by that theory, we create a way to fail model where we wait until we notice that a student is falling behind before we intervene. The issue here is that for students who have learning difficulties in reading the cost of waiting until later years to identify a reading difficulty is far too great. Research suggests that delayed development of reading skills affects vocabulary growth leads to missed opportunities to develop comprehension strategies, Moreover, it alters the students' attitudes and motivation to read.

And if that's not bad enough children who exhibit qualities of being a poor reader by the end of their first year of primary school, almost never acquire average level reading skills by the end of primary school. So why have we not always taught explicit phonics instruction. The argument around this issue is that explicit phonics instruction is not required because not every student needs the same amount of instruction to be able to read. It's true some students will come to their first year of primary school already having a strong ability to read, but for students with reading difficulties being taught the foundations of reading is essential. Under the disability standards for education these showing curriculum legislates that teachers are to ensure that all students with a disability are able to participate in their showing curriculum on the same basis as their peers, through rigorous meaningful and dignified learning programs.

In recent years we've realized that reading is actually a very complex learnt skill and that explicit phonics instruction is beneficial for all early readers. A team of researchers in Scotland took 300 primary aged students from a low socio-economic area and put half through an explicit phonics program. The other half through a traditional phonics program for 20 minutes a day over seven years. They found that by grade seven the explicit +-phonics students were three years and six months ahead of their average reading age and seven months ahead of the students who learnt the traditional way. Not only that of the students who had taught the explicit phonics program, only 5.6 percent were more than two years behind the average reading age for grade seven.

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

So how do we let go of our traditional model and push towards a new and dynamic way of reading instruction? Schools have begun to adopt the three-tier RTL model, starting early intervention for at risk of failing readers. This model involves the explicit instruction of the five areas or pillars of reading phonological awareness:

- phonics;
- fluency;
- vocabulary;
- comprehension.

The first tier of the model is providing clear explicit instruction of the fire reading areas to the whole class. Tier 2 intervention offers a more intensified emphasis in smaller groups of students who are at risk of failing. If the first two tiers aren't successful, the student is placed into tier 3 where they are provided with one-on-one intensive reading instruction. The RTL model enables a full initial screening process for all students including measures which are highly predictive of later reading ability.

The word identification fluency test has been found to be the most reliable form of assessment and can be seen in the edcheckup which tests oral reading fluency and takes about 15 minute and the more comprehensive early reading diagnostic assessment which tests a multitude of reading skills taking up to two hours.

However, teachers often have a good idea of what to look for when it comes to reading difficulties. A student with a reading difficulty may be:

- less engaged in reading tasks;
- less confident in their ability to read;
- less willing to take risks in reading out new words;
- frustrated with difficult work task;
- discouraged by their lack of success.

However, no single description or profile can represent all individuals with reading difficulties or learning difficulties as a whole. So what are going to be the best strategies for helping students with reading difficulties? Strategies need to focus on:

- decoding;
- increasing fluency;
- improving comprehension

Our aim is to help students read to learn. For students to decode the text they are reading they need to understand how the letters and sounds work. So use a phonics alpha chart along with phonemic games and exercises. The charts can even be put on the walls around the room for reference in class time. You have mnemonic devices to remember tricky spellings. Make it fun to build fluency. Create reading lists of high-frequency words and run an activity where the student reads as many as they can for one minute noting down how many correct words we've read. Doing this day after day will show the student that they are improving and succeeding. Reading aloud together as a class for around 10 to 15 minutes per day can also help the student practice phrasing and intonation. While there are many assistive technologies such as the speak tool from Microsoft and Mac and apps such as Claro speak plus and Claro PDF Pro which turns text into speech making it easier than ever for students to hear written text.

Reading is one of the most important types of communicative and cognitive activity aimed at extracting information from a written text. The receptive nature of this type of speech activity determines the availability and ease of its study.

There are a number of difficulties in learning a foreign language:

- when teaching foreign language reading, there are no strong auditory and motor images of the words being read in the memory of younger students;
- the need to master the system of graphic signs that differ from the signs of the native language, as well as the ability to correlate them with foreign language sounds;
- strive to develop students' cognitive interest in subject by involving them in various playable situations;
- to help recreate the situation of real communication on foreign language during the lesson.

CONCLUSION

To build comprehension pre teach vocabulary using class by using analogies synonyms or visual aids, have students use a dictionary or check online to confirm their correct use of harder words. Teach students how to generate questions without a text using a KWL chart, have students think pair and share their responses to questions. Help students to make connections to personal experience knowledge and previous reading. All of our work with helping students

with reading difficulties context is key. We need to contextualize our instruction to the content they are learning, allowing students to transfer their new reading skills to other learning situations. With early intervention and hard work we can stop students with reading difficulties being left behind in our schools. Thus, we analyzed the main problems of teaching reading in English at the initial stage of education, confirmed the need to teach children not only fluent reading skills, but also meaningful reading. In the process of studying the English language circle, students develop the reading skill with full reading comprehension and the skill of viewing reading, as well as increasing motivation and faith in their own capabilities.

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